

1-1 Lorentz Boost Mapping from Rest to Moving When a Moving Frame Only Implies a Velocity

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A Lorentz boost from a rest frame to a moving involves taking on (x,t) point in the rest frame (from many which one may choose) and multiplying it by a Lorentz matrix which yields only one solution, (x',t') corresponding to a choice of (x,t) . An issue with this approach is that in a moving frame ($-v$ constant) one should only see the object move with v . Measuring v requires two sets of measurement values (x_1',t_1') and (x_2',t_2') and so it is not clear why one should have a specific (x',t') . The Lorentz transformation assumes that $(0,0)=(x,t)$ means $(0,0)=(x',t')$, but we argue that this is too restrictive, although it does give a correct transformation for this particular scenario.

In fact, one might think one could see a moving particle at any x',t' in the moving frame.. The values x,t in the rest frame seem to be completely arbitrary and so it is not clear why one would not simply say that in one frame a particle is at rest and the second, that it is moving with constant v .

This issue seems to manifest itself if one uses the Lorentz matrix which links (x,t) to (x',t') to create the Lorentz invariant: $-m_0 c^2 t = -E't' + p'x'$. The issue here is that for a given t , there is not one solution of x',t' , but an entire set, x',t' or $x' + n \text{ constant}/p'$, $t' + n \text{ constant}/E'$. We have pointed this out before, but we suggest here that the reason for this degeneracy is the fact that in the moving frame one should only see motion v . This invariance statement, however, does not allow for any x',t' values, but only for a set of special ones with resolutions of $dx' = \text{constant}/p'$ and $dt' = \text{constant}/E'$. In other words, the Lorentz boost is actually associated with a resolution scheme which suggests that the moving object itself is associated with this same resolution scheme.

In order to determine the constant linked to this resolution, we suggest that one may start with a Lorentz transformation for a rest mass m_0 situation and consider what happens if rest mass disappears either through setting it to zero or using E/p in which it naturally cancels.

Moving Frames

An object at rest in one frame will be seen to be moving at constant v (velocity) by a frame moving at $-v$. The x,t values in the rest frame may be chosen in a completely arbitrary manner and the same should hold for the moving frame because all one needs is to see the object move at v . Thus, a Lorentz transformation which takes a specific (x,t) and maps it to a single (x',t') seems to be over-restrictive. If this statement is true, it would imply that any x',t' value is acceptable, but this statement means that one has infinite resolution for x' and t' , which is certainly consistent with Newtonian thinking.

If one considers a particle with rest mass m_0 to be at $x=0$ at t with $v=0$, then in a moving frame ($-v$ constant) it moves with v . If one formally uses $v = (x_2' - x_1') / (t_2' - t_1')$, then this is the usual way of defining constant speed. If one suggests that there exists a matrix transforming x,t to x',t' , then one may use $x=0, t=0$ in the rest frame and have it map to $x'=0, t'=0$. This suggests that

$x'_1=0$ and $t'_1=0$ and so $v = x'_2/t'_1$. In other words, $(0, t)$ in the lab frame should transform to (x', t') such that $v=x'/t'$. The problem with this scheme is that physically one does not have the rest frame and the moving frame both see $(0,0)$. One may use any x, t to describe the object in the rest frame and any x', t' to describe it in the moving frame if one only wishes to note that it moves with v . The linking of $(0,0)=(x, t)$ with $(0,0)=(x', t')$ seems to be over-restrictive and we suggest that one should the physical idea of multiple x', t' emerge. Such a scenario, however, does not occur if one simply multiplies (x, t) by a Lorentz matrix, but it does appear in the Lorentz invariant:

$$-m_0 c^2 t = -E't' + p'x' \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is completely consistent with the Lorentz mapping of x, t to a single x', t' , but it also holds for any (x, t) and compatible (x', t') . We have argued that physically there should be multiple x', t' values, but ((1)) shows that in fact there are, but that there is a built-in resolution namely:

$$x' = x'_1 + n * \text{constant}/p' \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad t' = t'_1 + n * \text{constant}/E' \quad ((2b))$$

Here n is an integer. In other words one considers the idea of resolution and repetition.

Thus, not any x', t' is allowed. Using the multiple solutions ((2a)) and ((2b)) seems to be in keeping with the physical idea that the moving frame need only see the particle move with v . The new idea, however, is that time and spatial resolutions are imposed. These time resolutions are linked to the quantum mechanical view of a free particle described by $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, but we have discussed this in previous notes. Here we only wish to stress the physical reason for taking the degenerate solutions ((2a)) and ((2b)) seriously. They are based on the physical idea that the only real physical restriction is that the moving frame sees the particle move with v . The equation ((1)), however, imposes a second restriction seen in ((2a)) and ((2b)) which is the quantum mechanical view.

Fixing the Constant in ((2a,b)) and b in ((1))

A problem still exists because the constant in ((2a,b)) and b in ((1)) are not fixed. To fix these, one may use two approaches. First, if one sets $m_0=0$, then ((1)) implies that $0 = -E't' + p'x'$ or $x'/t' = v = E'/p'$. This is the speed of a particle with no rest mass.

Next, for a particle with rest mass: $E' = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ and $p' = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ from the Lorentz transformation ((3)).

A particle with no rest mass has $v=E'/p'$ so setting $m_0=0$ in ((3)) means that $1-vv/bb=0$ to have an indeterminate form which may or may not have a solution. (It must have a solution if a particle with zero rest mass exists.) Thus, b is the maximum value v may take and it is frame invariant. This is a key idea.

The next step is to take E/p for a particle with rest mass. Then m_0 disappears naturally as if there were no rest mass:

$E/p = bb/v$ ((4)) This must equal the speed of the particle with no rest mass.

The largest value of v is b , $bb/b =$ speed of the particle with a rest mass of 0.

One may then argue that this particle is a photon which has speed c in a vacuum. This speed must be frame invariant as argued above. Furthermore, experiments in the early 1800s showed that light behaves as a wave, thus: $v = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength}$. This is of the same form as $v = E/p$ if $E = \text{constant1} * \text{frequency}$ and $p = \text{constant1} / \text{wavelength}$. Experiments with light show that $\text{constant1} = \hbar$. The frequency and wavelength, however, are in keeping with the argument of finite resolution of time and space given above, so \hbar should also be the constant used in ((3)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, although we have argued many times that $\text{constant} = -Et + px$ leads to multiple degenerate solutions $x + n * \text{constant}/p$ and $t + n * \text{constant}/E$, we suggest here that this degeneracy is to be expected because a particle at rest is only seen to be moving with v by a frame moving at constant $-v$. It is too restrictive to argue that $(0,0)$ in the rest frame is $(0,0)$ in the moving frame which is what is implied by the use of the Lorentz transformation. The transformation is correct for this specific case, but the result is not general enough. One should have an entire set of x', t' values. Interestingly, the Lorentz invariant: $-m_0 c^2 t^2 + p^2 x^2$ yields the infinite set of x', t' required, but with specific spatial and temporal resolutions: \hbar/p and \hbar/E . Thus, a moving object is linked with these specific resolutions. This yields the quantum mechanical view, but we argue here that it follows directly from the physical notion that a moving frame ($-v$ constant) only sees the particle move with v .